

DIGITALIZATION AS ONE OF THE FACTORS TO INCREASE INCLUSIVE ECONOMIC GROWTH

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13960329>

In the contemporary global economy, digitalization has transformed not only how businesses operate but also how economies grow and develop. Digital technologies, including the internet, artificial intelligence, blockchain, and big data, have fundamentally reshaped industries, improved access to services, and boosted productivity across various sectors. The digital economy, which thrives on these technologies, has become a cornerstone of modern economic development, offering significant opportunities for both developed and developing countries to foster more inclusive growth.

Inclusive economic growth refers to a model of growth that ensures that the benefits of economic expansion are distributed equitably across society, improving the well-being of all citizens, especially marginalized groups. Digitalization, by enabling broader access to information, services, and markets, plays a critical role in achieving this goal. Through digital tools, underserved populations gain access to education, financial services, healthcare, and employment opportunities that would otherwise be unavailable. This makes digitalization not only a driver of growth but also a mechanism for reducing inequality and enhancing social inclusion.

Despite its potential, digitalization also presents challenges that could exacerbate existing inequalities, such as the digital divide—the gap between those who have access to digital technologies and those who do not. To ensure that digitalization contributes to inclusive economic growth, policymakers and stakeholders must address these disparities by promoting digital literacy, expanding digital infrastructure, and ensuring equitable access to technology.

The link between digitalization and economic growth has been well-documented in academic literature. For example, a study by the McKinsey Global Institute found that digital technologies could contribute up to \$2 trillion in annual global GDP growth by 2025, with significant benefits for both developed and developing countries [1]. The study emphasizes that digital technologies boost productivity by enabling businesses to optimize their operations, reduce costs, and access new markets.

Similarly, the World Bank's *World Development Report 2016: Digital Dividends* highlights the role of digital technologies in driving economic growth

by fostering innovation and entrepreneurship. The report argues that countries that invest in digital infrastructure and promote digital skills development are more likely to experience higher rates of economic growth [2]. However, the report also warns that without proper policies, the benefits of digitalization may be concentrated in the hands of a few, exacerbating inequality.

Moreover, digital financial services help reduce transaction costs and improve efficiency, enabling small businesses and entrepreneurs to access credit and grow their enterprises. Research conducted by the International Finance Corporation (IFC) shows that digital financial services can increase GDP growth by 2-3% in emerging markets, primarily by improving access to credit for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) [3].

Education is another area where digitalization has a profound impact on inclusive growth. Digital learning platforms, such as massive open online courses (MOOCs), have democratized access to education, allowing people from different socioeconomic backgrounds to access high-quality learning materials. A report by UNESCO emphasizes that digital technologies have the potential to bridge the education gap between rural and urban areas, providing opportunities for lifelong learning and skill development [4].

The potential for digitalization to create new job opportunities is another important factor in fostering inclusive growth. The rise of the gig economy, powered by digital platforms has provided flexible employment options for millions of people around the world. These platforms enable individuals to offer services or freelance work without being bound by traditional employment structures, providing income opportunities for those who may have been excluded from the formal job market [5].

However, while digitalization can create jobs, it can also displace workers in industries that are more vulnerable to automation. According to a report by the World Economic Forum, while digital technologies will create 133 million new jobs by 2025, they may also displace 75 million jobs, particularly in low-skilled sectors [6]. This highlights the importance of reskilling programs and social safety nets to ensure that workers are not left behind in the transition to a digital economy.

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